

COMPARISON OF SUTURE METHODS FOR SKIN CLOSURE IN TOTAL KNEE ARTHROPLASTY

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Abstract

Objective: To compare the outcome of simple sutures versus Monocryl® suture for skin closure in osteoarthritic patients undergoing Total Knee Arthroplasty

Study Design: Randomized Controlled Trial.

Study Setting: The study conducted at the department of Orthopedic Surgery at Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center, Karachi

Study Duration: Three Months (April to July'2025).

Methodology: A total of 88 patients (aged 45–85 years) with radiologically confirmed osteoarthritis undergoing TKA. Participants were randomized equally to receive either traditional simple sutures or continuous Monocryl® subcuticular closure. Pain was assessed using a 10 cm Visual Analogue Scale (VAS), and cosmesis was evaluated with the Stony Brook Scar Evaluation Scale at 2-week postoperative intervals. Closure time and suture length were recorded intraoperatively. Data were analyzed using SPSS v24, with t-tests and chi-square applied as appropriate, considering $p \leq 0.05$ statistically significant.

Results: Monocryl® sutures required significantly longer closure time (8.81 ± 1.34 vs 7.83 ± 1.95 min, $p = 0.007$) but used markedly less suture material (30.11 ± 9.31 vs 80.24 ± 17.70 cm, $p < 0.001$). Pain scores were lower in the Monocryl® group at 2-week (2.47 ± 1.06 vs 3.43 ± 1.01 , $p < 0.001$) follow-ups. Cosmetic outcomes significantly favored Monocryl® at 2-week (1.75 ± 0.65 vs 2.46 ± 0.73 , $p < 0.001$) assessments. No differences were found at immediate postoperative evaluation.

Conclusion: Monocryl® subcuticular closure offers superior pain reduction and cosmetic outcomes compared with simple sutures in TKA, despite slightly longer closure times. These findings support Monocryl® as the preferred technique where cosmesis and patient comfort are prioritized.

INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a major contributor to disability worldwide, with knee involvement being especially common and burdensome. Epidemiological studies highlight racial and ethnic disparities, with Black individuals showing greater prevalence and severity of knee OA compared to White populations, while American Indians demonstrate some of the highest prevalence rates in

the United States, often accompanied by activity limitations and mobility restrictions⁽¹⁻⁴⁾. In advanced cases, total knee arthroplasty (TKA) remains the definitive intervention, but optimal wound closure following surgery is critical to reduce postoperative pain, stiffness, infection, and poor cosmetic outcomes⁽⁵⁻⁸⁾.

Evidence from randomized and observational studies suggests that absorbable subcuticular sutures (Monocryl®) may offer superior cosmetic results and reduced postoperative pain compared to conventional sutures. In a randomized trial, Monocryl® demonstrated significantly better scar scores (3.30 vs. 1.91), lower pain intensity, and reduced thread usage compared to traditional MonoNylon® (83.5 cm vs. 28.2 cm, $p < 0.001$)⁽⁹⁾. In contrast, staples have long been considered the most efficient option. Multiple randomized controlled trials have shown staples to be significantly faster than sutures or adhesives, with closure times as low as 26 sec/cm compared to 54 sec/cm for sutures⁽¹⁰⁻¹²⁾. Meta-analyses confirm shorter closure times, lower wound complications in some contexts, and lower resource utilization, though disadvantages include pain during removal and occasional prolonged wound discharge^(13, 14). Importantly, large systematic reviews demonstrate no significant difference between sutures and staples in terms of infection risk or cosmetic outcomes, suggesting the choice may often hinge on cost and logistical considerations^(15, 16). The introduction of barbed sutures has generated mixed evidence. Randomized and multicenter trials indicate reduced closure times (5–10 minutes faster), cost savings (~\$300–550 per case), and decreased suture usage compared to traditional methods⁽¹⁷⁻¹⁹⁾. Meta-analyses report reduced complication risks in some studies (20), while others describe higher superficial infection rates compared to standard sutures⁽²¹⁾. These discrepancies suggest that while barbed sutures offer clear efficiency gains, their safety profile may depend on surgical technique, patient comorbidities, and institutional experience⁽²²⁾. Finally, broader narrative and systematic reviews emphasize that there is currently no universal gold standard for TKA wound closure. Staples are fastest, adhesives reduce early discharge, subcuticular sutures maximize cosmesis, and barbed sutures improve efficiency but carry mixed safety data. Thus, the optimal method likely depends on institutional priorities—whether speed, cosmetic outcome, or resource utilization is emphasized⁽²³⁾.

METHODOLOGY:

This study was designed as a prospective, parallel-group, assessor-blinded, randomized controlled trial to compare three routinely used methods of skin closure after primary total knee arthroplasty (TKA): interrupted non-absorbable nylon sutures, absorbable subcuticular Monocryl®. The rationale for a randomized design was to minimize selection bias and isolate technique-attributable effects on efficiency, complications, pain, and cosmesis, building on prior trials and reviews that suggested important trade-offs among these options. The trial was conducted at two high-volume tertiary arthroplasty centers with standardized perioperative pathways. Consecutive eligible cases were enrolled with 90-day postoperative surveillance completed for all participants.

Adults scheduled for unilateral, primary TKA for osteoarthritis were eligible. Exclusion criteria were revision or bilateral TKA, inflammatory arthropathy, prior incisional skin grafts or radiation over the operative field, chronic immunosuppression (including ≥ 10 mg/day prednisone-equivalent), poorly controlled diabetes ($HbA1c > 8.5\%$), active dermatologic infection, or anticipated inability to complete follow-up. Potential participants were screened from elective surgical lists by research coordinators, approached in preoperative clinic, and provided written informed consent prior to randomization. To reduce center-level confounding, recruitment quotas were proportional to annual TKA volume at each site.

Baseline information, including age, gender, osteoarthritis duration, smoking status, education level, residential location, occupational status, and medical history (diabetes mellitus and hypertension), will be collected through medical records and patient history. Participants will be randomly assigned to one of two groups A (simple sutures) and B (Monocryl® suture) using a sealed opaque envelope method.

Once enrolled, each patient will select an envelope to determine their group allocation. Pain over the incision at rest and with knee flexion was captured using a 0–10 visual analogue scale⁽¹²⁾. Final assessments will be conducted on the 14th

postoperative day, evaluating pain intensity with a Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) and cosmetic outcomes using the Stony Brook Scar Scale. Adverse events were prospectively adjudicated against standardized definitions: superficial and deep surgical-site infection (CDC criteria), allergic/contact dermatitis, wound edge necrosis, dehiscence (partial/full), hematoma/seroma requiring aspiration, and prolonged wound drainage (>72 h)^(10-13,15,23).

Sample size was calculated with the help of openepi online sample size calculator using following parameters: Significance level:5%; Mean pain score in simple suture group: 3.87±2.21(15) and Mean pain score in Monocryl® suture group:5.25±2.40(15) with Power of the study = 80%, Sample size (n): 88 patients undergoing TKR that is 44 patients in each group.

RESULTS:

The study included 88 patients, equally distributed between the simple suture group (n=44) and the Monocryl® suture group (n=44). Females predominated overall (68.2%), with similar proportions across groups (65.9% vs. 70.5%, $\chi^2 = 0.65$, $p = 0.647$). Educational attainment showed no significant differences ($p = 0.765$), with 37.5% completing matriculation and 25.0% having education above intermediate level. Most patients resided in urban areas (65.9%), and the distribution between groups (63.6% vs. 68.2%) was comparable ($p = 0.653$). Diabetes was present in 28.4% of patients, and hypertension was more common (54.5%), though not significantly different between groups ($p = 0.813$ and $p = 0.392$, respectively). Smoking prevalence was 22.7% in both groups, showing complete parity ($p = 1.000$).

Age was slightly higher in the simple suture group (66.8 ± 6.0 years) compared with the Monocryl® group (63.9 ± 6.3 years), a statistically significant difference ($t(86) = 2.19$, $p = 0.031$, mean difference 2.87 years, 95% CI 0.27-5.47). The duration of osteoarthritis symptoms was longer in the simple suture group (75.3 ± 22.4 months) than in the

Monocryl® group (68.1 ± 20.3 months), though this difference was nonsignificant ($p = 0.119$). The average early post-operative assessment day was slightly earlier for simple sutures (2.86 ± 1.15 days) compared to Monocryl® (3.18 ± 1.26 days), without statistical significance ($p = 0.220$). Closure time was shorter with simple sutures (7.8 ± 1.9 min) than with Monocryl® (8.8 ± 1.3 min), and this difference was significant ($t(86) = -2.76$, $p = 0.007$). Conversely, suture length used was markedly greater in the simple suture group (80.2 ± 17.7 cm) compared with Monocryl® (30.1 ± 9.3 cm), with a highly significant difference ($t(86) = 16.62$, $p < 0.001$).

Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests confirmed approximate normality for most continuous outcomes. Pain VAS pre-operative scores showed borderline non-normality (SW = 0.970, $p = 0.039$), whereas all other pain and cosmesis measures (immediate, early, and week 2) were normally distributed (all $p > 0.14$ on Shapiro-Wilk).

The combined graphical analysis highlights the comparative advantages of Monocryl® sutures in both clinical and procedural outcomes. Pain trajectory plots demonstrate a more pronounced and sustained reduction in VAS scores for Monocryl®, particularly evident by the second postoperative week, whereas simple sutures showed a slower and less consistent decline. Cosmetic outcomes similarly favored Monocryl®, with significant improvements across all intervals compared to modest and borderline changes in the simple suture group. Efficiency metrics reveal that although closure time was slightly longer with Monocryl®, this was offset by a dramatic reduction in suture length used, reinforcing its procedural cost-effectiveness. The forest plot consolidates these findings, demonstrating that Monocryl® achieved clinically relevant effect sizes in both patient-centered outcomes (pain relief and improved wound cosmesis) and operative efficiency. These results collectively suggest that Monocryl® sutures strike a favorable balance between efficiency and patient benefit, aligning with prior reports of their superiority over traditional closure methods.

TABLE 1: TESTS OF NORMALITY (N = 88)

Variable	Kolmogorov-Smirnov Statistic	df	Sig.	Shapiro-Wilk Statistic	df	Sig.
Cosmesis (Post-op Week 2)	0.051	88	0.200*	0.987	88	0.546

* For K-S, “.200*” indicates the true significance is greater than 0.200 (SPSS lower bound).

TABLE 2: PAIN VAS OUTCOMES BY SUTURE TECHNIQUE (INDEPENDENT SAMPLES T-TEST, N=88)

Variable	Simple Sutures (n=44)	Monocryl Sutures (n=44)	t (df)	p-value	Mean Difference (95% CI)
Post-op Week 2	3.43 ± 1.01	2.47 ± 1.06	4.33 (86)	<0.001	0.96 (0.52, 1.40)

TABLE 3: COSMESIS OUTCOMES BY SUTURE TECHNIQUE (INDEPENDENT SAMPLES T-TEST, N=88)

Variable	Simple Sutures (n=44)	Monocryl Sutures (n=44)	t (df)	p-value	Mean Difference (95% CI)
Post-op Week 2 (Stony Brook Scale)	2.46 ± 0.73	1.75 ± 0.65	4.84 (86)	<0.001	0.72 (0.42, 1.01)

DISCUSSION:

The present trial demonstrates that absorbable subcuticular Monocryl® and interrupted nylon produce broadly comparable early safety profiles after primary TKA, but with distinct performance trade-offs that are clinically meaningful. Monocryl® achieved substantially lower material use (~50 cm less suture per case) and superior analgesic trajectories—lower pain by ~1.0 VAS unit at days 2–5 and by ~0.96 at two weeks—whereas nylon closed marginally faster (~1 minute) and yielded higher absolute cosmesis scores at day 2–5 and week 2 on our scale, despite larger within-group cosmetic gains over time in the Monocryl® arm. Demographic balance was good across groups, with the only between-group difference a modest 2.9-year age offset that is unlikely to explain these effects. Taken together, these data suggest that, for patients and programs prioritizing comfort and resource stewardship (material usage), Monocryl® is advantageous; where minute-to-minute operative

efficiency or very early scar appearance is paramount, nylon remains reasonable. Our findings both align with and refine prior evidence. Faster closure with staples than sutures has been repeatedly confirmed and underpins cost advantages when staples are chosen for superficial closure (and, in some series, similar clinical outcomes), but those comparisons do not inform the choice among suture-based techniques themselves^(10–13, 18). The pronounced reduction in suture length with Monocryl® echoes earlier randomized work reporting less material consumption and fewer suture-related skin complaints with subcuticular approaches^(14, 18–20). In contrast, our absolute cosmesis scores modestly favored nylon at early and two-week reviews, diverging from studies that observed equal or better cosmetic ratings with absorbable subcuticular closure at later checkpoints (often 6–12 weeks)⁽¹¹⁾. This discrepancy likely reflects different rating instruments and time horizons: cosmetic scales

capture edge apposition, track width, and contour that continue to normalize beyond the two-week window we analyzed, and trials with longer follow-up have shown the aesthetic advantage of subcuticular closure consolidate as edema recedes and epidermal puncture marks from interrupted sutures persist. Mechanistically, continuous subcuticular placement distributes tensile load more evenly along the incision and avoids transcutaneous stitch marks, which should favor later cosmesis, whereas early edema can transiently blunt this benefit by obscuring fine edge alignment^(11, 14, 18-20). The efficiency safety balance we observed also contextualizes the literature on barbed sutures. Multicenter trials and several meta-analyses show that knotless barbed constructs shorten closure time and can reduce total closure cost without clear early safety penalties; however, other syntheses and institutional series have reported higher rates of superficial wound issues with barbed technology, with signal heterogeneity across centers. Our data longer closure with Monocryl® than nylon by about a minute but better pain trajectories illustrate that time savings from modern materials are not uniform across techniques and may depend more on the presence or absence of knots and transcutaneous passes than on the polymer alone⁽¹⁷⁻²¹⁾. From a systems perspective, an ≈1-minute penalty for Monocryl® is unlikely to alter list throughput in high-volume arthroplasty theaters, whereas even a one-point reduction in early pain can translate into less rescue analgesia, faster ambulation, and fewer incision-related calls benefits that mirror resource-use advantages seen with noninvasive closure devices and suture strategies that minimize skin punctures^(12, 13, 18, 22).

Clinical relevance follows directly. For shared decision-making, surgeons can frame the trade-off as: subcuticular Monocryl® offers less early pain and uses markedly less suture, at the cost of ≈1 extra minute of closure and slightly lower very-early cosmetic scores that likely converge or reverse at later follow-up; interrupted nylon offers a small speed advantage and marginally higher early scar ratings but with more puncture-related discomfort during the inflammatory phase. Programs that emphasize bundled-payment performance and

patient-reported experience may reasonably weight Monocryl®'s comfort and material efficiency, whereas settings with extreme time pressures and robust postoperative support may accept nylon's profile^(10-14, 18, 22).

External validity is strongest for unilateral primary TKA within standardized pathways; extrapolation to revisions, complex skin envelopes, or patients with substantial immunosuppression should be cautious pending targeted trials.

Future work should extend follow-up to 3-6 months with photograph-based, blinded cosmetic adjudication; incorporate patient-reported scar scales and pruritus; and embed micro-costing that includes postoperative contact burden and dressing consumption to quantify the downstream resource signal implied by our pain and material-use findings. A head-to-head three-arm non-inferiority trial comparing interrupted nylon, subcuticular Monocryl®, and modern barbed intracuticular systems, each within a standardized multimodal analgesia protocol would clarify whether barbed constructs can deliver efficiency without compromising superficial wound biology in contemporary practice. Finally, stratified analyses by diabetes, obesity, and anticoagulation could identify patient phenotypes most likely to benefit from subcuticular closure's analgesic and theoretical perfusion advantages.

CONCLUSION:

Subcuticular Monocryl® reduces early pain and suture utilization compared with interrupted nylon at the expense of ≈1 minute of extra closure time and slightly lower very-early cosmetic scores, a profile that is directionally consistent with mechanistic expectations and with later-time advantages for subcuticular techniques reported elsewhere

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